

USE OF PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CAPACITIVE TRANSDUCER IN DETERMINATION OF WATER CONTENT IN CRUDE OIL

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада электр сизимли конденсаторнинг физик хусусиятларидан фойдаланган ҳолда хом нефть таркибидаги сув миқдорини аниқлашнинг икки усули кўриб чиқилган. Нефть таркибидаги сув миқдорини аниқлаш учун индикатор сифатида актив ва реактив элементлардан ташкил топган электр схема ишлатилган. Бунда сизимнинг муҳит диэлектрик киритувчанлигини ўзгаришига асосланган ҳолда аниқлаш усули кўриб чиқилган. Ушбу мақола орқали ўлчаш схемаси ва ҳисоблаш формулалари берилган.

Калит сўзлар: нефт, хом нефть, муҳитни диэлектрик киритувчанлиги, конденсатор реактив қаршилиги, қаршилиқлар учбурчаги.

Аннотация: В данной работе рассмотрена два способа определения содержания количества воды в сырой нефти с помощью электрофизических свойств электрических конденсаторов. В качестве индикатора определения влажности нефти использована электрическая схема состоящих из активных и реактивных элементов. Ёмкость конденсатора на прямую связана с диэлектрической проницаемостью исследуемого объекта. Приведена электрическая схема измерения и расчетные формулы определения ёмкости.

Ключевые слова: Сырой нефть, диэлектрическая проницаемость, ёмкость конденсатора, реактивная сопротивление, треугольник сопротивлений, сдвиг фаз, фазометр.

Annotation: *In this paper, we consider two methods for determining the amount of water in crude oil using the electrophysical properties of electrical capacitors. An electrical circuit consisting of active and reactive elements was used as an indicator for determining the oil moisture content. The capacitance of the capacitor is directly related to the dielectric constant of the object under study. The electrical circuit of the measurement and calculation formulas for determining the capacitance are given.*

Keywords: *crude oil, dielectric permeability, capacitor capacitance, reactance, resistance triangle, phase shift, phase meter.*

It is important to determine the quality of oil products at the initial stages of production. One such quality indicator is the water content of crude oil, that is, the water content of crude oil is the main factor affecting its quality indicators. Determining the amount of water in oil is carried out using one of two methods, namely [1]:

- - using special sensors (electrodes) placed inside the pipelines during the flow of the extracted or transported product through oil pipelines;
- - testing of extracted oil in laboratory conditions of oil samples taken from special reservoirs.
- In both cases, we can use the physical properties of the capacitor element as sensors (electrodes) that carry out the measurement [2].

P 1. Two-electrode capacitance measurement sensor Capacitance of a known flat capacitor:

here:

$$C = \epsilon \epsilon_0 \frac{S}{d} \tag{1.1}$$

ϵ - dielectric permittivity of the medium;

ϵ_0 - dielectric constant;

S is the surface of the capacitor plate;

d is the distance between the capacitor plates (P. 2).

P 2. Parallel plate of flat capacitor

To carry out the measurement, we can consider the following circuit in the form of an electrical circuit [3].

P 3. Electrical scheme of the measuring sensor

is equal to Here: $\omega=2\pi f$ angular frequency [4]. The current passing through this part of the circuit I3:

$$I_3 = \frac{U_{ab}}{Z_3}; \tag{1.3}$$

Z3 is the total resistance in the circuit a) and b) part:

$$Z_3 = \sqrt{R^2 + X^2} \tag{1.4}$$

The X-reactive resistance is $X = X_s$ since this network consists only of X_s [5].

Based on the expressions given above, the change in the reactance of the capacitor leads to a change in the network current I3. If these quantities are connected together and given in the form of a graduation table, it will be possible to determine the amount of water in crude oil with high accuracy in laboratory conditions using a not so complicated scheme. allows you to determine the angle between [6]:

X is reactive resistance of the circuit;

R is the active resistance of the circuit;

Z – total resistance of electric circuit;

φ is the displacement angle between current and voltage.

The reactance X of the given circuit is directly related to the reactance X_s of

capacitor taken as an indicator, and its change leads to a change in the φ -shift angle [7].

$\text{tg}\varphi$ is found from the triangle of resistances $\text{tg}\varphi$.

here: $\varphi \equiv \arctg^X$;

R

We can measure the resulting φ angle with a phasometer, make a table of dependence on the amount of water in the product, and graduate it (Table) [8].

1-Table

tgφ град ус	X _c O M	W %
30	--	12
20	--	14
15	--	17
10	--	20+

As a conclusion, we can say that if we insert a substance or material whose capacitance should be checked between the plates (shells), then we can see that the dielectric permittivity of the medium between the plates changes to a certain extent, and this, in turn, leads to a change in the value of the capacitor's capacitance [9].

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